

TABLE 2—5-(2-OXO-3-INDOLINYLIDENE)-3-(DISUBSTITUTED)PHENYL-2,4-THIAZOLIDINDIONES^a(3)

Sl. No.	Substituents		m.p. °C	Colour and shape of crystals	Molecular Formula	%C Found (Calcd.)	%H Found (Calcd.)	%N Found (Calcd.)	Characteristic IR bands (cm ⁻¹)
	X	Y							
	2-CH ₃	5-Cl	277-79	Orange, small needles	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ ClN ₂ O ₃ S	58.43 (58.32)	3.41 (3.00)	7.72 (7.55)	3200(w), 1745(m), 1685(s), 1615(m)
2.	2-CH ₃	3-Cl	284-86	Bright orange, crystals	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ ClN ₂ O ₃ S	58.15 (58.32)	3.30 (3.00)	7.65 (7.55)	3275(w), 1750(m), 1690(s), 1645(s), 1620(s)
3.	4-CH ₃	3-Cl	>310 dec.	Orange, fine crystals	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ ClN ₂ O ₃ S	58.60 (58.32)	2.92 (3.00)	7.85 (7.55)	3215(w), 1740(m), 1675(s), 1655(s), 1615(m)
4.	2-Cl	3-Cl	323-25	Brick red, microcrystals	C ₁₇ H ₉ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₃ S	52.01 (52.19)	2.29 (2.06)	6.93 (7.16)	3400(m), 1745(m), 1690(s), 1620(m)
5.	2-Cl	4-Cl	161-62 ^b	Orange yellow, powder	C ₁₇ H ₉ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₃ S	51.86 (52.19)	1.93 (2.06)	7.18 (7.16)	3300(w), 1740(m), 1700(m), 1645(s), 1620(m)
6.	2-Cl	5-Cl	266-68	Orange red, fine crystals	C ₁₇ H ₉ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₃ S	51.90 (52.19)	2.23 (2.06)	7.40 (7.16)	3450(br,w), 1740(m), 1690(m), 1640(s), 1615(s)
7.	2-OCH ₃	5-Cl	275-76	Bright orange, long needles	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ ClN ₂ O ₄ S	55.85 (55.90)	2.91 (2.86)	6.96 (7.24)	3400(br,w), 1745(m), 1685(s), 1615(w)
8.	4-OCH ₃	3-Cl	330-33	Deep orange, fine crystals	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ ClN ₂ O ₄ S	56.18 (55.90)	3.05 (2.86)	7.02 (7.24)	3200(w), 1740(m), 1675(s), 1615(m)

^a Yields were in the range of 80-95%.

^b Shrinks at 130°.

round bottom flask. The flask was immersed in an oil bath preheated to 150-160°. The reaction mixture became orange at this temperature and within 10 min orange crystals began to appear. Heating under reflux was continued for 3 hr. It was then cooled and treated with excess of hot water. The thioindigoid dye was filtered and washed successively with hot water, dilute acetic acid and finally with ethanol. Recrystallization from ethanol afforded orange needles, yield 90%, m.p. 277-79°. Anal. Found: C, 58.43; H, 3.41; N, 7.72. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₁ClN₂O₃S; C, 58.32; H, 2.99; N, 7.55%. IR (nujol): 3200 (w, N-H stretch), 1745 (m, C=O stretch), 1685 (s, C=O stretch), 1615 (m) cm⁻¹.

The general procedure exemplified above was employed for synthesis of all the thioindigoid dyes. Their properties and characteristic ir spectral bands are reported in Table 2.

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Reaction of Ninhydrin with Aromatic Amines and Ureas

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THE reactions of ninhydrin (I) with aromatic amines were studied by a number of workers¹⁻⁴. Several reports are available on the reactions of ninhydrin with ureas⁵⁻⁷. The objective of our present investigation was to have some qualitative idea about the reactivity of ninhydrin towards nucleophilic addition using poor organic nitrogen nucleophiles and to prepare various conjugated systems from these reactions. In continuation of our previous studies⁸⁻¹⁰ on the reactions of ninhydrin, we report here the syntheses of compounds (II)-(VII). These compounds appear to be new and are not reported in the literature.

Structures were assigned to these compounds on the basis of their nitrogen content, ir spectral data (Table 1) and formation of derivatives. 2,4-DNP did not react with the second carbonyl group of the mentioned compounds probably due to steric hindrance^{8,10}. Compounds (II) and (IV) gave positive Lucas test indicating the presence of tertiary-OH groups. It is not clear why the adduct (II) in the case of α -naphthylamine did not undergo dehydration while the condensation product (III) was obtained in the case of β -naphthylamine. One probable explanation may be that the steric interaction due to the naphthalene ring becomes sufficiently strong to prevent the formation of the planar structure for the condensation

TABLE I—IR ABSORPTION BANDS (in cm^{-1}) OF COMPOUNDS (II-VII)

(II)	3600 (b), 3400 (b) (OH, NH), 1690 (C=O), 1605 and 1570 (aromatic)
(III)	1760 and 1700 (C=O), 1630 (C=N), 1580 and 1525 (aromatic)
(IV)	3500 (b), 3400 (b) (OH, NH), 1710 (C=O), 1620 and 1590 (aromatic)
(V)	1710 (C=O), 1620 (C=N), 1600 and 1650 (aromatic)
(VI)	3320 (b), (NH), 1725 and 1690 (C=O), 1670 (C=N), 1600 and 1580 (aromatic)
(VII)	3600, 3300 and 3200 (b) (NH), 1725 (C=O), 1600 (C=N), 1590 and 1575 (aromatic), 1460 and 1450 (C=S)

product (IX). Unlike *p*-aminophenol and *p*-phenylenediamine⁸ the addition product (IV), formed in the case of *o*-anisidine, was not dehydrated completely under the conditions used to give (V), possibly due to less resonance stabilization of the *o*-quinonoid structure than the *para* structure. Compounds (VI) and (VII) gained stability due to conjugation as a result of which the nucleophilicity of the amido nitrogen decreased and no further reaction took place. No reaction of ninhydrin was observed with 2,3-diaminotoluene, *o*-chloroaniline and *m*-nitroaniline in aqueous medium even at the refluxing temperature and using dilute H_2SO_4 as the catalyst. Inertness of these compounds may be due to a decrease in the electron availability of the amino nitrogen, primarily due to the steric effect, in the case of 2,3-diaminotoluene and -I effect due to Cl and $-\text{NO}_2$ group in the case of *o*-chloroaniline and *m*-nitroaniline, respectively.

Experimental

The formation of products from the various reactions was followed by tlc on silica gel plates using benzene-ethyl acetate (80 : 20) for α - and β -naphthylamines, methylurea and thiourea; benzene-chloroform (90 : 10) for *o*-anisidine, 2,3-diaminotoluene and *o*-chloroaniline; benzene-methanol (95 : 5) in the case of *m*-nitroaniline. The ir spectra were run as nujol mulls, except in the cases of (IV) and (V) where the spectra were run in CHCl_3 , using a Unicam SP 1025 spectrophotometer. All the reactions were conducted in a manner analogous to the reaction of α -naphthylamine.

Reaction of ninhydrin with α -naphthylamine. Formation of 2-hydroxy-2-*N*-(α -naphthylamino)-1,3-indandione (II): Ninhydrin (1.78 g; 0.01 mole) in water (50 ml) was added slowly to α -naphthylamine (1.42 g; 0.01 mole) in water (50 ml). The mixture was stirred at room temperature (24°) for 76 hr. The yellow precipitate formed was filtered off, washed thoroughly with water, dried under vacuum, recrystallised from ethanol, and obtained as (II), m.p. 283-284°, yield 73% (Found: N, 4.12. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_3\text{N}$; N, 4.62%). The 2,4-DNP derivative crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 296-298° (Found: N, 14.25. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_6\text{N}_5$; N, 14.49%).

Reaction of ninhydrin with β -naphthylamine. Formation of 1,3-diketohydrindylidene-2- β -naphthylamine (III): A yellow coloured product (III) was obtained which was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 225-227°, yield 62% (Found: N, 4.47. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_3\text{N}$; N, 4.91%). The oxime derivative crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 168-170° (Found: N, 12.68. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_3\text{N}_2$; N, 13.33%).

Reaction of ninhydrin with *o*-anisidine. Formation of 2-hydroxy-2-*N*-(*o*-methoxyphenylamino)-1,3-indandione (IV) and 1,3-diketohydrindylidene-2-*o*-methoxyphenylamine (V): The reaction mixture was stirred for 57 hr. A brown coloured product was obtained, m.p. 80-82° (decomp.), which showed five spots in tlc, two of which corresponded to *o*-anisidine and ninhydrin. The product was purified by preparative tlc and two products (IV) and (V) were isolated, yields 25% and 40%, respectively. Compound (IV), R_f value 0.41, m.p. 86-88° (Found: N, 4.63. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_4\text{N}$; N, 4.94%). The 2,4-DNP derivative had m.p. 102-104° (Found: N, 14.87. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_7\text{N}_5$; N, 15.11%). Compound (V), R_f value 0.81, m.p. 90-92° (Found: N, 4.97. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_3\text{N}$; N, 5.28%). The 2,4-DNP derivative had m.p. 143-145° (Found: N, 15.10. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{15}\text{O}_6\text{N}_5$; N, 15.73%).

Reaction of ninhydrin with methylurea. Formation of 1,3-diketohydrindylidene-2-*N*-methylcarbamide (VI): The reaction mixture was stirred for 105 hr. A white solid was isolated as (VI) which was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 249-250°, yield 60% (Found: N, 12.62. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_8\text{O}_3\text{N}_2$; N, 12.96%). The 2,4-DNP derivative crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 268-269° (Found: N, 20.91.

Calcd. for $C_{17}H_{12}O_6N_6$; N, 21.21%. Its ir spectrum showed bands at 3280 (NH), 1690 (C=O), 1620 (C=N), 1610 and 1590 (phenyl), 1375 and 1336 (NO_2) cm^{-1} .

Reaction of ninhydrin with thiourea. Formation of 1,3-diketohydrindylidene-2-thiocarbamide (VII): The reaction mixture was stirred for 70 hr. A white precipitate obtained as (VII) was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 228-229°, yield 64.5% (Found: N, 12.40; S, 15.02. Calcd. for $C_{10}H_6O_2N_2S$; N, 12.84; S, 14.67%). The 2,4-DNP derivative crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 247-249° (Found: N, 20.62; S, 7.76. Calcd. for $C_{16}H_{10}O_5N_6S$; N, 21.10; S, 8.04%).

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Potential Antithyroid Agents. Part-II : Synthetic and Pharmacological Studies on Some N-Aryl-N'-2(benzimidazolyl) thiocar- bamides and N-aryl-N'-benzenesulphonyl- thiocarbamides

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THE antithyroid agents lower the metabolic rate by interfering with the synthesis, release or peripheral action of the thyroid hormone. Highly active antithyroid substances contain thiourea moieties, -NHCSNH-, capable of being easily oxidized and it has been suggested that the interference with thyroxine synthesis is by direct reaction between I_2 and SH (formed by enolization) to form a disulphide¹⁻⁴.

The present communication deals with the synthesis and pharmacological studies of some

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N-aryl-N'-2(benzimidazolyl) thiocarbamides and N-aryl-N'-benzenesulphonylthiocarbamides. The active antithyroid drug is carbimazole consisting of an imidazole nucleus. Therefore, it was of interest to prepare some benzimidazolyl thiocarbamides consisting of a benzimidazole nucleus alongwith an extra thioureylene group, by the action of arylisothiocyanates with 2-aminobenzimidazole. The interest in the synthesis and pharmacological studies of benzenesulphonylthiocarbamides as antithyroid drug is due to the fact that these compounds contain an extra sulphonamide grouping alongwith the thioureylene linkages. The synthesis has been effected by the condensation of benzenesulphonyl-isothiocyanate with appropriate aromatic amines.

Experimental

Melting points were determined with a Kofler hot stage apparatus and are uncorrected. IR spectra were obtained using KBr pellets and a Perkin-Elmer 720 Infracord spectrophotometer; bands reported were at least of medium intensity. Elemental analyses were in good agreement with the theoretical values.

Arylisothiocyanates: These have been prepared according to the method reported in the literature⁵.

Benzenesulphonylisothiocyanate: It has been synthesised by the method of McFarland and Houser⁶.

N-Phenyl-N'-2(benzimidazolyl) thiocarbamide: A mixture of phenylisothiocyanate (2.7 g; 0.02 mole) and 2-aminobenzimidazole (2.66 g; 0.02 mole) in dry benzene (25 ml) was refluxed for 2 hr. After the reaction, the excess benzene was distilled off and the residue was washed with petroleum ether (40-60°) and finally with ether to remove any unreacted constituents. N-Phenyl-N'-2(benzimidazolyl) thiocarbamide thus formed was recrystallised from ethanol. It could be desulphured with alkaline plumbite solution, yield 4.2 g, 80%; m.p. 110°. Anal. Found: C, 62.62; H, 4.38; N, 20.82; S, 11.90. Calcd. for $C_{14}H_{12}N_4S$; C, 62.68; H, 4.47; N, 20.89; S, 11.94%.

Other N-aryl-N'-2(benzimidazolyl) thiocarbamides were prepared similarly by the condensation of 2-aminobenzimidazole with different arylisothiocyanates.

The various N-aryl-N'-2(benzimidazolyl) thiocarbamides were characterised by elemental analyses. Presence of characteristic bands of $N=C=S$ (1520 cm^{-1}) and substituted benzene ring (780 cm^{-1}) in the ir spectra of these compounds provided further confirmation of their molecular structure.

N-Phenyl-N'-benzenesulphonylthiocarbamide: A solution of aniline (1.86 g; 0.02 mole) in benzene (20 ml) was gradually added to a solution of benzenesulphonylisothiocyanate (3.98 g; 0.02 mole) in benzene (20 ml). After few min a white precipitate of N-phenyl-N'-benzenesulphonylthiocarbamide was formed, which was collected and washed with benzene, petroleum ether (40-60°) and finally with